

SITE GPR	YEAR 2010	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 63.0264 Max: 63.1229	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1271 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	
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In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Photos: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #: 1198-1200	Photo Model: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No #:
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DEFINITION <i>fill of a round cut below "Marco"</i>	Covered by <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 1182	Fills <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 1276	Filled by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:
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HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Color <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Composition <input type="checkbox"/> Compaction	FORMATION PROCESS <input type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition
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INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are			SOIL/MATRIX clay 5% silt 80% sand 15% <input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive
Anthropic	Geological	Organic	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pottery R <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tiles R <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Amphorae R <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Glass	<input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)	<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Animal bones R <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	Compaction <input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft
			Color <input type="checkbox"/> Black <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)		Depth: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original
Northern Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Southern Limit	<input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	<i>→ Grave, Marco</i>
Western Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Eastern Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE	
Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by:	Abuts:
Is covered by: 1182	Covers: Bedrock 7001
Is cut by: 1197	Cuts:
Is filled by:	Fills: 1276

OBSERVATIONS *Half visible fill of a potential round pit sitting below the grave "Marco".*

DESCRIPTION
Position within sector: *South of Area B - South-eastern side of Room 2.*
Shape: *ROUND - SEMICIRCULAR*

For layers complete this section:
Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions): *Very light slope North-South. Visible inclusions of pottery and medium rocks.*
Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope)
Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):
Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

Excavation Limit (Southern End)

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

Fill of an Anthropoc pit where "Morco"s grave has been dug into.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by	MORGANE	on	27.07.2010
Revised by	CMN	on	28.07.2010
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Entered by		on	